

LEARNING ENGLISH WITHOUT MEMORIZING WORDS

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Abstract. Problems arise 95% of language learners worldwide start learning of language. The main reason for this is in the artificial learning of language. For instance, mastering grammar through formulas, memorizing words by listing, solving tests are included in artificial learning. And the natural way of learning is that we learn from childhood by listening to our mother tongue and learning through the influence of others. The main purpose of the article is to learn English easily without memorizing any words, natural learning methods and their advantage. In accordance with this goal, the following tasks identified as to increase the enthusiasm of children and language learners of different ages through the use of natural learning methods and increase the effectiveness of lessons as a result of the use of these methods.

Key words: Language learners, artificial learning, memorizing words, natural learning methods, effectiveness of lessons.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА БЕЗ ЗАУЧИВАНИЯ СЛОВ

Аннотация. 95% изучающих язык по всему миру начинают изучать язык с проблем. Основная причина этого — искусственное обучение. Например, освоение грамматики с помощью формул, запоминание слов путем перечня, решение тестов — всё это относится к искусственному обучению. Естественный же способ обучения заключается в том, что мы учимся с детства, слушая родной язык и учась под влиянием других. Основная цель статьи — легко выучить английский язык без заучивания слов, естественные методы обучения и их преимущества. В соответствии с этой целью определены следующие задачи: повысить энтузиазм детей и изучающих язык разного возраста посредством использования естественных методов обучения и повысить эффективность уроков в результате применения этих методов.

Ключевые слова: изучающие язык, искусственное обучение, запоминание слов, естественные методы обучения, эффективность уроков.

Language learners can have various difficulties and problems in learning English such as:

- Forgetfulness of memorized words and vocabulary
- Ignorance of natural learning methods

Learning English in the modern world begins in kindergarten. There will be assimilation of information for children so that they acquire basic knowledge (alphabet, flower names, animals, objects). After that the language is learned in school, but the children do not put enough effort into learning English during this period.

Conscious learning of the language begins at University or after graduation. At this age, most people understand that learning a foreign language has many advantages, but most learners face problems. For example to learn English, you must memorize words. Anyone who wants to learn a language first makes a list of the words to memorize and starts memorizing it every day. Language learners learn new words every

day, but after few days they forget the words. As a result, their enthusiasm for language learning decreases. English vocabulary is an important part of learning and understanding the English language. English language learners are inundated with English vocabulary every day in the real world through movies, media and daily life. A student's vocabulary grows over time and compiling vocabulary lists from resources like books or other texts and materials is a great way to strengthen vocabulary.

Students as we know, they spend about 11 to 12 years in primary and secondary school learning English language. However many of them are still not able to master the language after completing the secondary school. Therefore there are various factors that contribute to this failure. For example, learner's learning methods, lesson plan and etc.

Everyone suffers from their own ignorance. And the only cure for ignorance is knowledge.

There are many different ways a person can learn something. You need to know what the most important things are that you should be learning, you need to know exactly what knowledge is, and know why knowledge is important

The aim of the study using suitable method for teaching various topics will enhance the effect of teaching. Some of the methods of teaching English are as follows:

- The Direct Method
- The Grammar Translation Method
- Audiolingual Method

The direct method of teaching English is also known as Natural method. It is used to teach a number of different languages not just English. Its main focus is oral and it is taught via repetitive drilling.

The basic premise of the Direct Method was lots of oral interaction, spontaneous, use of language, and little or no analysis of grammatical rules.

Richards and Rodgers summarized the principles of Direct Method:

- Classroom instruction was conducted exclusively in target language
- Only everyday vocabulary and sentences were taught
- Oral communication skills were built up in a carefully graded progression organized around question and answer exchanges between teachers and students in small, intensive classes

- Grammar was taught inductively
- New teaching points were taught through modeling and practice
- Concrete vocabulary was taught by association of ideas
- Both speech and listening comprehension were taught
- Correct pronunciation and grammar were emphasized.

The Grammar Translation method. This is traditional and classic way of learning a language and it is still commonly used when learning some languages. The language learners learn all grammar rules, so they are able to translate a number of sentences.

Prator and Celce-Murcia listed the major characteristics of Grammar Translation:

- Classes are taught in the mother tongue , with little active use of the target language

- Much vocabulary is taught in the form of lists or isolated words

- Reading of difficult classical texts is begun early

The Audiolingual Method was firmly grounded in linguistic and psychological theory. The aim of this method may be summed up in the follows

- New material is presented in a dialogue form

- There is dependence mimicry, memorization of set phrases , and over learning

- Structural patterns are taught use repetitive drills

- Vocabulary is strictly limited and learned in context .

In order to be more independent and efficient learner the students need to be aware of how languages are learned and what their own preferred learning style is- how they learnt best. They also need to be aware of certain study skills and strategies for learning so they can choose which work best them. A number of strategies when practicing language learning skills -strategies which they are using language independently of the classroom and teacher. Some example of these techniques and strategies :

Listening

- ✓ Making an effort to predict what they are going to hear

- ✓ Choosing the appropriate „way” listening depending on the purpose ,eg for overall understanding, specific details.

- ✓ Using techniques of facilitating listening when taking part in conversation (eg asking for repetition, clarification)

Reading

- ✓ Choosing appropriate, ways”of reading depending on the text and purpose for reading(eg skimming, scanning)

- ✓ Using strategies for deducing the meaning unknown words in a reading texts

- ✓ Using dictionaries efficiently

Speaking

- ✓ Using strategies for facilitating speaking such as paraphrasing, appropriate, „fillers” etc

Writing

- ✓ Making notes and organizing them before doing a piece of „ free” writing

- ✓ Making a rough draft first and going back and trying to improve it

- ✓ Identifying their own mistakes by symbols

Learning style are the general approaches - for example global and analytic, auditory or visual - that students use in acquiring a new language or in learning any other subject. Sensory preferences can be broken down into four main areas: Visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile.

The purpose of this paper is to use different styles in language learning. some researchers have identified different perceptual styles :

- The visual

- Aural

- The tactile and kinesthetic
- Reading / writing learners

Visual learners usually enjoy reading and prefer to see the words that they are learning. They also like to learn by looking at pictures and flashcards .

1. Slide shows
2. Posters
3. Clips
4. Watch a movie
5. Doodle diagrams of your written information in the margins
6. Makes flashcards that include pictures or diagrams as visual clues
7. Highlight key information in your texts or notes
8. Use a computer to convert data and notes into charts, tables, graphics, pictures ,etc.
9. Timelines

Auditory learners learn rely primarily on music and sound for their learning .Information is often best acquired through verbal lectures, discussion and mini presentations.

- Use a computer to record your notes read aloud. Convert this information to download for iPod using iTunes

- Singing /creating songs
- Listening songs , movies ,radio and audio books
- Read your notes aloud when studying
- When learning new material, especially equations, talk your way through the material

- Tape lectures. If available, set the counter to zero when it begins and note the number at difficult times during lecture. Review these recorded times later for extra review

- Use a metaphor / similes to compare and remember (as long as they are voiced)
- Work in a group where you can discuss the information

Kinesthetic learners learn by touching and manipulating objects - this is known as <<hands-on>> work. Hands -on activities and real life experiences help them remember.

- As much as possible, create models for the information at hand
- When possible, visit location for your material (library, museum, historical sites,etc.)
- Write your notes onto flashcards -scrabble, - make posters
- Review flashcards while walking, at gym, etc.
- Walk back and forth, move in some way, when studying notes
- To learn a sequen or equation, use one note card for each step
- Correlate physical movements with ideas/terms

Reading /writing learners. They comprehend and remember what they read, and they often enjoy writing.

- Re-write your notes after class

- Use colored pens and highlighters to focus in on key ideas
- Write out key concepts and ideas
- Compose short explanations for diagrams, charts, graphs
- Print out your notes for later review
- Post note cards/post-its in visible place (when doing dishes, on the bottom of the remote, etc.)
- Compare your notes with someone else's
- Repetitive writing

In conclusion, we try and discuss easy learning of English using different styles without just memorizing words. The most opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of the teaching.

According to the above mentioned material, we can say that knowledge about effective teaching.

It is obvious that the use of language learning styles allows you to learn and speak fluently using short and easy methods.

It is in the hands of the language learners learn the English language in an effective manner.

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